

Correlation of non-academic activities and the academic performance of BSA students: An evaluation of extracurricular activities in preparation for board examination

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Abstract

Involvement in extracurricular activities has an impact on kids' academic achievement. Extracurricular activities (ECAs) have grown in importance within the educational experience for pupils, with many schools devoting substantial financial resources to them. Data regarding the background variables were gathered using a documentary analysis and questionnaire to correlate non-academic activities with academic performance. The main purpose of this study is to evaluate the extracurricular activities for board programs, and at the end of the study, the researcher found out that there is no significant difference when grouped according to year level as to the factors of achieving a satisfactory grade, consuming time for study, and completing classroom work with regards to institutional activities. There is also no significant difference when grouped according to year level as to the factor of achieving a satisfactory grade with regards to school activities because students perceive that school activities somewhat help them in some aspect of their courses, while as to the factors of consuming time, studying, and completing classroom work, there is a significant difference when they are grouped according to their year level.

Keywords: Correlation; Extracurricular activities; Academic performance; Board program.

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Introduction

Extracurricular (ECA) activities are those that students participate in outside of the requirements for graduation. Hobbies and social, athletic, cultural, or spiritual interests may be among them. They are somewhat organized and have certain advantages. It is expected that ECAs will improve students' experiences, help them grow their soft skills, assist them in managing stress, and give them further advantages to boost their job opportunities (Veronesi & Gunderman, 2012).

A study looked at earlier research on the effect of ECA involvement on students' academic achievement in a variety of educational literature. Three main theoretical frameworks were proposed based on a literature review: first, because students were spending more time on ECA activities than on their academic studies, the zero-sum framework proposed that ECA involvement had a detrimental impact on academic achievement. Second, the developmental framework claimed that because of the social and non-academic advantages of engaging in extracurricular activities, engagement in ECAs indirectly improves academic achievement. Finally, the threshold framework argued that academic performance is positively impacted by ECA participation up to a certain extent, after which participation results in unfavorable academic consequences (Seow & Pan, 2014).

According to Al-Ansari et al. (2016), it is obvious that addressing issues in educational settings generally, and those pertaining to ECAs specifically, requires a customized strategy. Adaptation to individual variances across educational institutions, program kinds, specialization fields, and characteristics of learners, including cultural and social experiences, is important. In the research that Al-Ansari et al. (2016) conducted, the students' participation in ECA was minimal. Differently between the two institutions, ECA participation was impacted by gender and how ECAs were seen in connection to academic subjects. It is necessary to better develop and oversee ECAs, considering the preferences and motivations of the students involved. School and societal aspects should be considered when discussing gender-related issues and the connection between ECAs and academic achievement. The aim of the research was to assess the extent of the effect of non-academic activities on the academic performance of accounting students. Its correlation and evaluation of the performance of the accounting students as a purpose in preparation for the board examination.

Only a small percentage of students from each of the dental schools that were part of the study took part in ECAs that were run by them or on their own. They gave these activities minimal attention and prioritized sports, community service, and other activities that highlighted their social features. The majority of students did not believe that ECAs interfered with their academic work or damaged their marks. Students in this study failed to employ ECAs to reduce stress, despite the fact that learning environments are known for raising stress levels.

One enduring problem in the public education system is the role of student activities. Non-classroom activities conflict with learning in school for students' time and attention, according to certain supporters of educational reform. The underlying premise of such an argument is that youth activities and academic success are causally related. In a study by Camp (1990), using the sophomore cohort data set, the researcher looked at the potential causal association between academic achievement and a student's level of extracurricular and co-curricular activity participation. The model under investigation looks at the effects of academic standing, family history, gender, and other conflicting time-use patterns. The results raise concerns about the reasoning behind policies that prohibit academically marginalized kids from participating in extracurricular and co-curricular activities and imply that student engagement improves academic attainment.

According to a study by Chua et al. (2017), there is a relationship between the quantity of positions and the quantity of first interviews. The degree of involvement is correlated with the development of innovative and creative skills. This indicates that the respondents' degree of involvement in extracurricular activities of all kinds can boost their capacity for creativity and innovation. Critical thinking and problem-solving abilities are correlated with collaboration and team-building abilities. This demonstrates how the development of an individual's critical thinking and problem-solving abilities also leads to the development of their teamwork and collaboration abilities. This is appropriate for situations in which a single person is collaborating with a group. Critical thinking and problem-solving abilities are correlated with proficient time management. This demonstrates how the development of critical thinking and problem-solving abilities also leads to the development of effective time management abilities. Collaboration and team-building abilities are correlated with knowledge of information and technology. This demonstrates how the development of information and technology-related abilities also leads to the development of teamwork and collaboration skills. This is appropriate for situations in which a single person is collaborating with a group. Effective time management abilities are correlated with expertise in information and technology. This implies that the development of information- and technology-related skills occurs concurrently with the development of good time management skills. There is a relationship between good time management and leadership abilities. There is a positive correlation between the two independent variables. This implies that a person's ability to manage their time effectively develops along with their leadership abilities (Chua et al., 2017).

Although a great deal of research has been done in the literature to study the effects of ECA involvement, little of it has been done in the context of accounting education. The current study is to add to the body of knowledge in accounting education by investigating the effect of ECA involvement on the academic achievement of students in a college accounting program. This will broaden the scope of the usually studied determinants to include things like prior academic success, aptitude for mathematics, critical thinking, age, gender, previous accounting expertise, and work experience. In order to expand the body of research on the factors influencing students' academic achievement in the accounting education literature, the researcher encourages others to carry out additional studies on the effects of ECA involvement (Seow & Pan, 2014).

Hermano (2016) believes that students involved in non-academic activities have a more positive impact on their academic performance. Joining activities in the school that are not related to the subjects enables the students to socialize well, which aids in developing their social skills. Being involved allows individuals to show effort, cooperation, and teamwork.

A study by Sulaiman (2016) observed that engineers have been concerned with student retention for a long time. In one of the historically black colleges and universities (HBCU) in a Mid-Atlantic state, this study looked at academic and non-academic characteristics that affect undergraduate turnover in electronic engineering, other STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) courses, and non-STEM majors. Academic characteristics and student retention were found to be statistically significantly correlated, according to the current study's correlational analysis results. Nonetheless, no statistically significant correlation was observed between non-academic characteristics and the retention rate of students.

This supports the research done by Craft (2012), which has demonstrated that involvement in extracurricular activities can yield numerous benefits for students' academic performance and accomplishments. Students who participate in extracurricular activities acquire important skills related to the "hidden curriculum" of these extracurriculars. Students gain knowledge of time management, teamwork, commitment, and how to form wholesome bonds with parents, instructors, coaches, and community members. These characteristics are applied to every pursuit that a student pursues, including academic success. Extracurricular activities should not be discontinued by schools, since doing so can actually lower student achievement.

This study aims to determine the correlation of non-academic activities and academic performance of the BSA students and evaluate the extracurricular activities for board programs. Specifically, this research answers the following questions:

1. Profile of the respondents
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Academic year level
2. How do respondents perform in their academics, with regards to their major courses, as:
 - 2.1 Financial accounting and Reporting 1
 - 2.2 Financial Accounting and Reporting 2
 - 2.3 Advanced Financial Accounting and Reporting 1
3. How do respondents perceive non-academic activities, in terms of:
 - 3.1 Institutional activities?
 - 3.1.1 As a factor in achieving satisfactory academic grade
 - 3.1.2 As a factor consuming time elements to study
 - 3.1.3 As a factor to complete classroom work
 - 3.2 Departmental activities?
 - 3.2.1 As a factor in achieving satisfactory academic grade
 - 3.2.2 As a factor consuming time elements to study
 - 3.2.3 As a factor to complete classroom work

4. Is there a significant difference on the perception of the respondents to non-academic activities and academic performance, when grouped according to academic year level?
5. Based from the findings, what are the recommendations necessary to limit co-curricular activities for Board Examination Program?

The impact of extracurricular activities on the academic performance of students has been widely debated over the years. Some say that impact is positive, while others say it is negative. The study aims to identify the significant relationship of the extracurricular activities to academic performance and determine whether there is a need to lessen the extracurricular activities for board programs based on the perceptions of the respondents with regard to the factors of the non-academic activities.

The study was conducted at St. Dominic College of Asia. The respondents are the selected students who participated in any institutional or college activities: third- and fourth-year BSA students who already took Financial Accounting 1 and 2 and Advanced Financial Accounting 1. Data were collected through a documentary analysis and survey. The researcher aims to distinguish the correlation between non-academic activities and academic performance.

Figure 1. Relationship between variables

The research paradigm exemplifies the relationship between variables in this study. The study aims to inform the respondents of the effect of non-academic activities on their academic performances and the factors affected by the extracurricular activities. The study specifically hopes to shed light on the significance of the extracurricular activities in the academic performance of board programs and the perceptions of the students with regards to the factors indicated in the non-academic activities.

Methodology

The study employed causal-comparative research. In the causal comparative study, the researcher looked at cause-and-effect correlations between the variables and how the dependent factors affect the independent variables. With respect to the dependent variable, the factorial design emphasizes more than one category with independent variables (Vogt & Johnson, 2016).

Additionally, the study employs quantitative methods that emphasize objective measurements and mathematical, numerical, or statistical analysis of data gathered via surveys, polls, and questionnaires, as well as the use of computational techniques to manipulate pre-existing statistical data. Determining the causal relationship between an independent and dependent variable is the aim of quantitative research. Classifying features, counting them, and creating statistical models are the primary goals of quantitative research, which aims to explain observed phenomena (Babbie, 2020).

The study used quantitative methods, and the researchers designed a survey form as a data collection instrument. The survey questions aimed to determine the extent of affection for non-academic activities for academic performance. The data gathered will be counted to determine which factor of academic performance is highly affected by the extracurricular activities. The study was made during the second semester of the academic year 2018–2019 at St. Dominic College of Asia. The sample is composed of 20 selected students who participated in any institutional or college activities for the academic year 2017–2018. They are the third- and fourth-year BSA and BSAT students who are done taking Financial Accounting 1 and 2, and Advanced Financial Accounting 1.

A systematic sampling technique was used for selecting the participants of the study. The participants were identified based on their characteristics that suit the purpose of the study. The survey was conducted at St. Dominic College of Asia. They were selected based on their participation in non-academic activities both in school and at the institution. Hence, the BS Accountancy students were chosen specifically.

The researcher used the following as a data collection instrument:

1. **Questionnaire:** The survey or questionnaire consists of two categories of non-academic activities: institutional activities and college activities. Under these categories are selected factors concerning academic performance:

- achieving a satisfactory academic grade
- consuming time elements to study
- completing classroom work

2. **Documentary Analysis:** This study also required the grades of the respondents in their major subjects as a documentary analysis. The grades during the span of their participation in an extracurricular activity served as a guide to evaluate the significance of these activities in the BSA's academic performance.

Statistical Treatment

The statistical methods used to show the correlation between non-academic activities and academic performance are frequency distribution, ranking, and t-test to determine the differences when grouped according to their year level.

1. **Frequency Distribution:** A frequency distribution is a list, table, or graph that displays the frequency of various outcomes in a sample. Each entry in the table contains the frequency or count of the occurrences of values within a particular group or interval, and in this way, the table summarizes the distribution values in the sample.

2. **Ranking:** A ranking is a connection between a group of items in which the first item is either "ranked higher than," "ranked lower than," or "ranked equal to" the second for any given pair of items. The value's ordinal number in a list that is ordered in a particular way (typically decreasing) (Allison & Christakis, 1994).

3. **t-Test:** An inferential statistic called a t-test is used to see if there is a significant difference between the mean values of two groups that might be associated with specific characteristics. It is typically employed in situations where the data sets, such as the one containing the results of 100 coin flips, have unknown variances and would otherwise follow a normal distribution. As a technique for evaluating hypotheses, the t-test enables an analysis of an assumption that is relevant to a population (Bevans, 2020).

Table 1. Scale and measurement

Scale	5	4	3	2	1
Interpretation	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Moderate Extent	Lesser Extent	No Extent
Range	4.51-5.00	3.51-4.50	2.51-3.50	1.51-2.50	1.0-1.50

This study is divided into four phases. The four phases are defined extensively below:

Phase I: Survey. The researcher administered a survey on the extent to which non-academic activities affect the academic performance of the respondents. The survey aimed to determine if there is a significant difference between the non-academic activities and academic performance of the board program, Bachelor of Science in Accountancy.

Phase II: Documentary Analysis. After the survey, the researcher asked the respondents to send their grades in Financial Accounting and Reporting 1, Financial Accounting and Reporting 2, and Advanced Financial Accounting and Reporting 1, which are major courses taken by both third- and fourth-year students during the conduct of the study.

Phase III: Statistical Treatment. The statistical method used to show the significant difference between non-academic activities and academic performance when they are grouped according to their grade level is the mean value, scale, and measurement.

Phase IV: Recommendation. Finally, the researchers gave recommendations on whether to lessen participation in organizations and activities in both the school and institution to improve academic performance.

Results and Discussion

Table 2. Profile of the respondents (n=28)

Profile	Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Age	18-19	10	36%
	20-21	14	50%
	22 above	4	14%
Academic Year Level	3rd Year	10	36%
	4th Year	18	64%

Table 2 shows that 10 or 36% of the students aged 18-19 years old, 14 or 50% are 20-21 years old, and four (4) or 14% ages 22 years old and above. When the respondents are grouped according to their year level, 10 out of 28 or 36% are third-year students and the remaining 18 or 64% are fourth-year students.

Table 3. Respondents' academic performance

Subject	Third Year	Fourth Year
Financial Accounting and Reporting 1	83.4	82
Financial Accounting and Reporting 2	84.5	83.8
Advanced Accounting and Reporting 1	84.4	85.4

Based on the data, third-year respondents' average grade in Financial Accounting 1 is 83.4%, while the fourth-year respondents have 82% in Financial Accounting 2. The third-year respondents' average grade is 84.5%, and the fourth-year respondents have 83.8%. In Advanced Accounting 1 as a major course, third-year respondents' average grade is 84.4%, while the fourth-year respondents' average grade is 85.4%. A specialist area of accounting called financial accounting monitors the financial dealings of an organization. The transactions are documented, compiled, and shown in a financial report or statement, such as an income statement or balance sheet, using uniform rules (Averkamp, n.d.).

Table 4. Respondents' perception on non-academic institutional activities and the academic performance factors according to year level

Institutional Activities	Year Level	5	4	3	2	1	No. of Respondents	Mean Value	Interpretation
I. As a factor achieving satisfactory academic grade	3rd	0	8	15	6	0	10	2.9	ME
	4th	20	16	21	6	0	18	3.5	ME
II. As a factor consuming time elements study	3rd	10	16	12	0	0	10	3.8	GE
	4th	25	24	12	4	1	18	3.6	GE
III. As a factor completing classroom work	3rd	15	12	9	0	1	10	3.7	GE
	4th	25	16	21	2	1	18	3.6	GE

Table 4 shows the result of the respondents' perception of the three factors with regards to institutional activities and rated them in accordance with the extent of their affection for their academic performances: as a factor in achieving a satisfactory academic grade, as a factor in consuming time to study, and as a factor in completing classroom work. As a factor in achieving a satisfactory academic grade, both third- and fourth-year students perceive that non-academic institutional activities affect their academic performance to a moderate extent. As a factor consuming time elements of the study, both third- and fourth-year respondents perceive that non-academic institutional activities affect their academic performance to a great extent. As a factor in completing classroom work, both groups of respondents perceive that non-academic institutional activities affect their academic performance to a great extent.

Table 5. Respondents' perception on non-academic departmental activities and the academic performance factors according to year level

Departmental Activities	Year Level	5	4	3	2	1	No. of Respondents	Mean Value	Interpretation
I. As a factor achieving satisfactory academic grade	3rd	10	8	15	0	1	10	3.4	ME
	4th	20	16	18	4	2	18	3.3	ME
II. As a factor consuming time elements study	3rd	10	16	9	0	1	10	3.6	GE
	4th	15	24	24	2	0	18	3.6	GE
III. As a factor completing classroom work	3rd	10	12	12	2	0	10	3.6	GE
	4th	30	12	15	8	0	18	3.6	GE

Table 5 shows the result of the respondents' perceptions of the three factors with regards to school activities and rated them in accordance with the extent of their affection for their academic performance: as a factor in achieving a satisfactory academic grade, as a factor in consuming time to study, and as a factor in completing classroom work. Both third- and fourth-year respondents perceive that non-academic school activities as a factor in achieving a satisfactory academic grade affect their academic performance to a moderate extent. They perceive that non-academic school activities, as a factor consuming time elements study, affect their academic performance to a great extent. At the same time, they perceive that non-academic school activities, as a factor in completing classroom work, affect their academic performance to a great extent.

Table 6. Significant difference on the perception of the respondents to non-academic activities and academic performance

Academic Performance	Mean Value (3rd Year)	Mean Value (4th Year)	Overall Mean Value	Interpretation	t-value
Institutional Activities					
I. As a factor achieving satisfactory academic grade	2.9	3.5	3.2	ME	0.1753
II. As a factor consuming time elements study	3.8	3.6	3.7	GE	0.8537
III. As a factor completing classroom work	3.7	3.6	3.65	GE	0.6945
Departmental Activities					
I. As a factor achieving satisfactory academic grade	3.4	3.3	3.35	ME	0.2011
II. As a factor consuming time elements study	3.6	3.6	3.6	GE	0.0789
III. As a factor completing classroom work	3.6	3.6	3.6	GE	0.0287

Table 6 shows that significant difference between the perception with regards to non-academic activities and academic performance of the BSA students vary according to their year level.

The t-value of 0.1753, which is higher than the standard significant level, $\alpha = 0.05$, and lower than the critical value of 2.101, implies that there is no significant difference between the perception of the third and fourth year students (that institutional activity is a factor in achieving satisfactory academic grade) and their academic performance.

The t-value of 0.8536, which is higher than the standard significant level, $\alpha = 0.05$, and lower than the critical value of 2.101, implies that there is no significant difference between the perception of the third and fourth year students (that the institutional activity is a factor consuming time elements study) and their academic performance.

The t-value of 0.6945, which is higher than the standard significant level, $\alpha = 0.05$, and lower than the critical value of 2.101, implies that there is no significant difference between the perception of the third and fourth year students (that institutional activity is a factor in completing classroom work) and their academic performance.

The t-value of 0.2011, which is higher than the standard significant level, $\alpha = 0.05$, and lower than the critical value of 2.101, implies that there is no significant difference between the perception of the third and fourth year students (that the school activity is a factor in achieving a satisfactory academic grade) and their academic performance.

The t-value of 0.0789, which is higher than the standard significant level, $\alpha = 0.05$, and lower than the critical value of 2.101, implies that there is no significant difference between the perception of the third and fourth year students (that the school activity is a factor consuming time elements study) and their academic performance.

The t-value of 0.0287, which is higher than the standard significant level, $\alpha = 0.05$, and lower than the critical value of 2.101, implies that there is no significant difference between the perception of the third and fourth year students (that the school activity is a factor in completing classroom work) and their academic performance. This result also supports the study by Craft (2012) that, regarding the total grade point average, there was no statistically significant difference between students who participate in extracurricular activities and those who do not.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Most of the respondents are 20 to 21 years old and in their fourth year. This is the age when students are expected to be in college and about to finish. The grades of the third-year students are higher than those of the fourth-year students in Financial Accounting 1 and 2. However, fourth-year students' grades in Advanced Accounting and Reporting 1 are higher than the third-year students' grades. The third-year respondents' average grade in Financial Accounting 1 and 2 is higher than that of the fourth-year respondents because they have more time to study but are not different with the result in Advanced Accounting and Reporting 1.

The findings show that departmental activities affect both third- and fourth-year students to a great extent in terms of consuming time for study and completing classroom work. This implies that because of the numerous and successive non-academic departmental activities, the students are having difficulty managing their time. So it results in either submitting the classroom work late or not being able to submit the classroom work at all.

However, it seems ironic because, despite the fact that the two factors mentioned above affect the academic performance of the students to a great extent, the data also shows that, in terms of achieving a satisfactory grade, the non-academic activities only affect the students to a moderate extent. This implies that despite the students' participation in non-academic departmental activities, they seem to remain responsible for their academic requirements and are still able to achieve satisfactory grades.

This conforms to the statement of Saqib et al. (2018), who say that it was observed that few subject understudies had grade point averages (GPAs) below average, whereas the great majority have ordinary GPAs. Thus, it may be said that students' extracurricular activity time does not truly overlap with their academic time.

For institutional activities, it shows that there is no significant difference when grouped according to year level, the factors of achieving a satisfactory grade, consuming time, studying, and completing the classroom. This implies that institutional activities as well as non-academic activities do not affect the students mostly. Students can still perform well in departments despite their participation in different institutional activities.

There is also no significant difference when grouped according to year level as to the factor of achieving a satisfactory grade with regards to departmental activities because students perceive that departmental activities somewhat help them in some aspect of their courses. However, the departmental activities with the factors of consuming time, studying, and completing classroom work show that there is a significant difference when they are grouped according to their grade level. This shows that non-academic departmental activities go beyond the students' capabilities, resulting in problems with time management and non-compliance with classroom work.

The student should develop important life skills like how to manage time, how to choose helpful activities, and how to decline activities that will only add burdens. The school and the institution should understand the need to join or not join the activities they conduct. There is a need to put extra effort into their academic performance if they, the students themselves, willingly participate in any activity or organization. They need to see to it that their major subject will not compromise on their extracurricular activities.

The school administrators must evaluate the performance of the students and assess whether the non-academic activities are necessary for the program. If there is a need to lessen them in order to help the students concentrate on their studies, then do so. The institution's administrators need to see that not every activity is helpful for the students and becomes a burden to them. The main goal of the institution is to produce professionals in their field. The institution needs to understand that there are programs that require a lot of their attention, and this is where their academic performance becomes at risk.

Parents and students should understand that there are things beyond the control of their children, and the least they want to hear is downgraded words and insults. Pressure in the school and pressure in the house can sometimes cause poor academic performance for the students; therefore, just like the students, parents also need to be patient and more understanding of their limitations.

Future researchers should consider the targets of the board programs to greatly understand the effects of non-academic activities on the academic performance of the students, not just accounting students but the whole community of this institution. The result of this study will, likewise, contribute to paving the way for future researchers. This research can be an effective tool and reference for the researchers if they would like to make further research, especially on the correlation of non-academic activities to the academic performance of board programs at St. Dominic College of Asia.

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